

DETERMINING THE LEVEL OF INTEREST IN MUSIC IN CHILDREN FROM 2 TO 3 YEARS OLD DURING INTERACTION WITH PARENTS

Skuratovich Yulia Igorevna

*postgraduate student of the Department of
General and Preschool Pedagogy,
Belarusian State Pedagogical University
named after Maxim Tank
Minsk, Belarus*

Abstract

The article clarifies the importance of a child's musical interest. A diagnostic survey of parents of children aged 2 to 3 years is presented, revealing the level of interest in children in listening to music, which is proposed to be used by preschool teachers and music directors.

Keywords: interest in music, diagnosis of interest in music, musical perception, early age.

Musical interest is directed to the value sphere of the child's personality; it is a regulator of musical activity. Developing in early and preschool age, interest is a prerequisite for the formation of such elements of musical-aesthetic consciousness as aesthetic need, taste, ideas of beauty and contributes to the development of musical perception, the formation of the foundations of the child's musical culture. O. P. Radynova considers interest in the structure of musical-aesthetic consciousness. One of the results of the development of interest in music is the child's acquisition of initial value orientations and the development of an aesthetic attitude towards the art of music [2]. The study by O. N. Antsyrovich shows a statistically significant connection between manifestations of interest in the musical activity of children of senior preschool age with indicators of emotional responsiveness, musical thinking, and the success of children's musical activity, which allows us to consider interest as a system-forming quality in the structure of the foundations of a child's musical culture [1].

We have developed a diagnostic questionnaire for parents of children aged 2 to 3 years, which reveals the level of interest in children in listening to music. The questionnaire was developed in the online service for creating feedback forms Google Forms. Access link – <https://forms.gle/f7mtGjCEqvY8P2E19>. Parents need to go through it using technical devices, answering questions. The questionnaire consists of the following questions and suggested answers:

1. What importance do you attach to the problem of developing musical perception in your child?

a) Developing my child's musical awareness is important to me. I believe that developed musical perception sets the preconditions for the development of all musical abilities. In turn, musical abilities are closely related to mathematical, sensory and others, which also confirms the importance of developing musical perception.

b) I believe that developing a child's musical perception is not so important compared, for example, with speech and mathematical development.

c) I consider the development of musical perception unnecessary for my child.

2. Do you purposefully listen to music with your child?

a) Yes, we purposefully listen to music with our child.

b) No, we don't listen to music on purpose. However, we periodically turn on background music.

c) No, we don't listen to music on purpose, because we don't like doing it.

3. How often do you purposefully listen to music with your child?

a) We purposefully listen to music with the child every day or every other day.

b) We purposefully listen to music with the child once a week or month.

c) We purposefully do not listen to music with our children.

4. Does your child enjoy listening to music?

a) Yes, the child always listens to music with pleasure (even sings along and/or dances).

b) The child does not always listen to music with pleasure (from time to time he is indifferent to listening to music).

c) No, the child does not experience pleasure from listening to music (negative emotions arise when listening to it).

5. Does the child himself ask to turn on music in his free time, during games?

a) Yes, the child often asks to turn on music in his free time, during games.

b) The child himself does not ask to turn on the music due to undeveloped speech.

c) The child does not express a desire to turn on music in his free time, during games.

6. Are you developing an interest in music in your child?

a) Yes, I am developing an interest in music. We listen to music together, talk about it, play children's musical instruments, etc.

b) No, I don't develop an interest in music because I don't have knowledge about organizing this process.

c) No, I don't develop an interest in music, because I don't think it's necessary.

7. Does anyone purposefully engage in musical activities with the child (except for music classes in a preschool educational institution)?

a) Yes, the child attends special classes.

b) No, they do not purposefully engage in musical activities with the child, because there is no opportunity.

c) No, I don't purposefully engage in musical activities with the child, because I don't think it's necessary.

8. Do you and your child attend children's plays and musical performances? If so, what is the child's attitude towards them?

a) Yes, we do. The child enjoys going to children's plays and musical performances.

b) Yes, we do. However, the child does not like attending these events (he begins to cry and be capricious a short time after the start).

c) No, we don't visit because we don't want to.

The answers are subject to quantitative processing. For each answer under the letter «C» the subject receives 0 points; for answers with the letter «B», the subject receives 1 point; for each answer under the letter «A», the subject receives 2 points. Children who received 0-5 points have an insufficient level; a level close to sufficient refers to children with 6-11 points; children who score 12-16 points have a sufficient level.

In 2021, we tested this questionnaire for 47 parents. A sufficient level is typical for 9 respondents – 19%, a level close to sufficient for 31 respondents – 66%, an insufficient level belongs to 7 respondents –

15%. Analyzing the results of a survey of legal representatives of pupils, we drew attention to the fact that the majority of parents purposefully do not listen to music with children: 35 respondents (74%) spoke about the use of music as a «background». When listening to music purposefully or «in the background», 40 children (85%) do not always perceive it with pleasure (they are periodically indifferent to listening to music). The majority of parents do not develop an interest in music in their children: 39 respondents (83%) do not have knowledge about the organization of this process, which reflects the need to carry out work on their musical education.

This diagnostic questionnaire to determine the level of interest in listening to music in children aged 2 to 3 years is proposed to be used by subjects of the educational process (preschool teachers and music directors), because it is in the interest of the students that their further musical development and education depends.

References

1. Antsyrovich, O. N. Formation of the basics of musical culture of senior preschool children by means of musical folklore [Electronic resource] / O. N. Antsyrovich // Repository BSPU. - Access mode: <http://elib.bspu.by/handle/doc/699>. - Date of access: 03.12.2023.

2. Radynova, O. P. Musical education of preschool children : a textbook for university students / O. P. Radynova, A. I. Katinen, M. L. Palavandashvili. - Moscow : Academy, 1998. - 240 c.